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CHRONIC VENOUS DISEASE AND DIABETIC ANGIOPATHY: OVERLAPPING PATHOPHYSIOLOGY AND COMMONALITIES (literature review)

Abstract.

Chronic venous disease (CVD) and diabetes mellitus (DM) are highly prevalent and debilitating conditions affecting millions of individuals globally. The intersections between DM and CVD are not to be underestimated.

Despite differences in etiology, the risk factors and pathophysiology of both CVD and diabetic microangiopathy share a number of commonalities. In this review, we have highlighted the evident connection between CVD and DM in processes such as vascular abnormalities, inflammation, endothelial dysfunction, and modification of coagulation factors, etc.

We aimed to draw researchers' attention to these interrelations that may lead to meaningful concepts, enabling clinicians to take appropriate and timely measures for patients with co-existent CVD and DM in early diagnosis and reduction of the possible risks of further complications.

Key words: *chronic venous disease, diabetes mellitus, angiopathy.*

Chronic venous disease (CVD) and diabetes mellitus (DM) are highly prevalent and debilitating conditions affecting millions of individuals worldwide with a high global socioeconomic impact. Although these conditions are typically considered as separate entities, they often co-exist which may be important in both understanding their pathophysiology and determining the best treatment strategy. DM is twice as common in patients with CVD compared with the general population [19]. Notably, a large proportion of patients with DM present with venous disorders, although this is often overlooked. While diabetes mellitus (DM) and hyperglycemia are known to cause arterial thrombosis and vascular disease, evidence suggests that they may play a role in an increased risk of venous thromboembolism as an additional source of vascular disease. Patients with venous thromboembolism and DM have a higher risk of short-term and long-term mortality than patients without DM [30].

The etiology of CVD is polygenic, involving hemodynamic, genetic, and environmental factors which result in changes to the venous endothelium and structural wall as well as inflammation [3]. CVD encompasses a broad spectrum of morphological and functional abnormalities of the venous system. It ranges from mild clinical signs, such as telangiectasias or reticular veins, to severe manifestations, such as venous ulcerations. Clinical signs may affect any vein in the body, the venous system located in the lower limbs is often the most vulnerable structure to suffer CVD [8, 18]. Thereby, varicose veins are the most common manifestation of CVD [29]. Varicose veins (VVs) are characterized by twisted and dilated veins in the lower

extremities. If left untreated, this condition can lead to complications such as superficial venous thromboembolism (VTE), deep vein thrombosis, and venous ulcers. The severity of CVD is measured via the presence of specific clinical signs classified on the Clinical, Etiological, Anatomical and Pathophysiological (CEAP) system. Classes C3-C6 are designated as chronic venous insufficiency (CVI), which indicates advanced functional venous abnormalities (such as edema, skin changes, or venous ulceration) [8, 18].

Inflammation and endothelial dysfunction are commonly observed in DM as well, accompanied by hyperfiltration or vascular leakage [23]. DM adversely affects the microvasculature in multiple organs, leading to the development of diabetic microvascular complications (DmVC). DmVC is comprised of microangiopathies that can lead to organ dysfunction in the eye (diabetic retinopathy), kidney (diabetic nephropathy) and nerve (diabetic peripheral neuropathy). Studies have shown that there is a high prevalence of DmVC particularly where the use of preventative drugs is suboptimal. It is important to note that even after conventional treatment for T2DM, a residual risk (around 50%) for the development of DmVC still persists [28].

While DM is a multifactorial disease with a diverse etiology as well, the results of numerous studies have shown that patients with DM had an increased risk of VTE, but mainly due to other confounding factors [5, 12, 17]. It is a broad consensus that factors leading to blood stasis, hypercoagulable state, and endothelial cell damage in patients, such as cancer, surgery, immobilization, advanced age, obesity, lack of physical activity, a family history of diabetes, polycystic ovary

syndrome, a low birth weight for gestational age, ethnicity, prior gestational diabetes, a genetic predisposition, hypertension, dyslipidemia, drug treatments (including statins and corticosteroids), hormonal therapy, oral contraceptives [6], smoking habit, and rheumatic immune diseases can increase the risk of VTE in patients with DM [24, 35].

The most likely biological explanation for an association between VTE and DM is the sharing of common risk factors – clinical and haematological ones [25]. However, conflicting results have emerged from studies on the correlation of VTE with DM in recent years. Some studies suggested that diabetes does not increase VTE risk [21], while others reported a positive association between diabetes and VTE risk [12]. Considering that, current literature data on the role of DM in VTE prognosis and the relationship between DM and VTE were comprehensively analyzed by conducting searches on Google Scholar, Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed and Research Gate databases for relevant scientific research.

Co-existing prevalence and shared risk factors

Several clinical studies have revealed that diabetes is present in 11-30% of patients with CVD/CVI, up to twice the frequency observed in the general population (~9%).

2 recent studies have shown [16, 37, 43] that the type of diabetes may influence the risk of VTE, with patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus having a higher risk of VTE than those with T2DM.

Other studies have shown that a higher BMI increases the risk of VTE, while T2DM is usually closely related to a high BMI [16, 43]. Clinical data suggest that T2DM is a risk factor for CVI development in 30-50% of CVD patients. Co-existing T2DM may aggravate the severity of CVI. Diabetes appears to be more frequently observed in patients with more severe forms of CVI (C4-C6) in both females and males, with a significant association observed in females.

A study by Mani et al [25], involving 61 patients with diabetes (aged 30-80 years) attending an outpatient clinic, reported that 64-70% of patients suffered from deep venous incompetence in either the right or left lower limbs; a statistically higher incidence than that seen in the general population. Nearly 50% of patients had shorter venous filling time, while approximately 30% experienced reduced arteriovenous response. In Zhong et al's study [49] involving 170 patients with diabetes, the prevalence of early CVD (C0-C1) was 63,5%, with a greater risk of CVD observed in females compared to males (79,4% vs. 52,9%). Due to the long-term effects of diabetes on the microcirculation and neuron degeneration, approximately 30% of patients with diabetes also present with skin lesions [46].

There is also a possible correlation between CVD, diabetes, and neuropathy. A more severe state of CVI is observed in patients with T2DM and diabetic polyneuropathy (DPN) [4].

Overall, the presence of diabetic microangiopathy in the lower limbs aggravates microcirculatory changes caused by CVD, which can facilitate the development

of trophic changes and the progression of venous pathology. In certain circumstances, arterial disease may directly promote the risk of VTE. Data from a retrospective study involving 2,636 patients with CVD demonstrated that the co-existence of peripheral arterial disease (PAD) or metabolic disease significantly correlated with the development of advanced CVI [34]. Similarly, Matic et al. [27] reported that PAD is more frequent in patients with a severe form of CVD than in those without CVD. The frequency of stenotic atherosclerosis of the arteries of the lower limbs is also reportedly higher in patients with concomitant CVD pathology.

The abovementioned co-existing prevalence of CVD and diabetic microangiopathy may result from the fact that both entities share common risk factors. Many of the recognized risk factors for CVD, such as increasing age, family history, pregnancy, a sedentary, poor nutritional lifestyle, overweight or obesity, hypertension and smoking, are common contributory factors in the development of DM. Furthermore, patients with T2DM are more susceptible to the appearance and progression of CVD since they already have typical CVD characteristics, such as microcirculation disorder of the lower limbs, high BMI, arterial hypertension and endothelial dysfunction [5, 12, 17].

Furthermore, the type of drugs prescribed to treat patients with DM also affects the risk of VTE. Long-term oral administration of metformin and statins can significantly reduce the risk of VTE in patients with DM [11, 36]. At the same time, sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 inhibitors, DPP-4 inhibitors, glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists may not be significantly associated with VTE risk [41].

Commonalities in pathophysiology

Although CVD/ CVI and DM/DmVC have different etiologies, shared risk factors, are likely driven by a common pathophysiology. Both are associated with vascular wall remodeling, impaired blood flow, increased oxidative stress, vascular inflammation, increased vascular permeability, and endothelial dysfunction, as a result of various hemodynamic abnormalities (Fig.1).

Notably, a greater degree of remodeling of the vascular wall is observed in patients with concomitant DM and CVD than in patients with either disease alone. Long term uncontrolled T2DM (HbA1c>10%, diabetes duration >10 years) and concurrent diabetic macroangiopathy in the lower limbs are associated with a higher frequency of failure of valves in the lower extremities, pronounced trophic changes and, ultimately, higher CVI severity levels [46]. It appears that in patients with concomitant pathology, the presence of diabetic complications (macro- and microangiopathy of the lower limb, hyperglycemia and DPN) exacerbates the clinical picture of CVI due to arterial vascular wall remodeling and functional disturbance of the venous system, both of which promote the development of trophic changes and progression of venous pathology [32].

In both CVD and diabetic microangiopathy, vessel hypertension slows blood flow in capillaries prompting the increased expression of leukocyte adhesion molecules (VCAM-1), chemokines (TNF- α) and cytokines

(MCP-1), and a reduction in endothelium-derived NO. Leukocyte adhesion to capillary endothelium initiates an inflammatory reaction, changing the endothelial phenotype to a proinflammatory and prothrombotic state. The resulting endothelial dysfunction is an early manifestation of CVD that is also prominent in hypertension, metabolic syndrome, diabetes, PAD, and chronic kidney disease [26, 47]. Its presence is linked to structural defects of the microcirculation including microvascular rarefaction, with microinflammation and disturbances of endothelial cell permeability manifesting as early signs of organ deterioration. In patients with concomitant T2DM and CVD, microvasculature disturbances are associated with greater venous stasis and disturbances in capillary perfusion than in patients with CVD alone [33]. Patients with DM invariably show impaired endothelium-dependent vasodilation, suggesting that DM generates conditions that promote reduced blood flow and the development of hemodynamic abnormalities. Mechanisms leading to endothelial damage in DM, independent of the damage due to other cardiovascular risk factors, include insulin resistance, hyperglycemia and low-grade systemic inflammation. Importantly, endothelial dysfunction not only precedes atherogenesis, but may also predispose to arterial thrombosis. Microcirculatory endothelial cell activation is an important feature in all thrombotic microangiopathies. The roles of oxidative stress and vascular inflammation in the development of endothelial dysfunction are of vital importance, as both are major pathways through which risk factors in CVD and DM exert their damaging effects on blood vessels. Higher oxidative stress promotes vascular inflammation in both pathologies. Research also suggests that elevated glucose levels in patients with concomitant CVD and DM may increase oxidative stress, inducing endothelial dysfunction and impairing venoconstriction responsiveness [48]. These factors may explain why DM is the most important risk factor for early CVD and why blood glucose and lipid levels are associated with venous function of the lower extremities in diabetic patients [32, 33, 46].

One other commonality is the role of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), which is the most critical driver of vascular formation, as it is required to initiate the formation of immature vessels by vasculogenesis or angiogenic sprouting. Besides reflecting the severity of endothelial dysfunction in patients with CVD or diabetic microangiopathies, VEGF has been shown to increase microvascular permeability and is likely to be a contributory factor to functional and structural skin changes (lipodermatosclerosis in venous leg ulcers) [26, 47].

Edema syndrome and trophic changes in the lower limbs are predominant in patients with T2DM. Similarly, edema in CVD is the first sign of microangiopa-

thy. Furthermore, both patient populations are predisposed to local tissue hypoxia and leg ulcers due to the alteration of immune functions, structural changes of collagen and binders and possible concurrence with PAD and autonomic neuropathy. Epidemiology data show that approximately 70% of leg ulcers seen in clinical practice are caused by venous disease, with an estimated 20% occurring as a result of arterial insufficiency or mixed arteriovenous disease. Approximately 85% of diabetic foot ulcers are caused by DPN, often in the presence of PAD [4, 27, 46]. Insensitivity to pain and decreased perception of pressure occurs. Abnormal plantar pressure redistribution can make the situation even worse [1]. Anatomical foot deformity is seen in diabetic patients, including hammertoes, loss of arch, and rocker bottom feet associated with Charcot's foot, while impaired microcirculation causes a breakdown of the skin and leads to ulcer formation. The process of wound healing is difficult due to a lack of adequate blood flow and concomitant deep tissue or bone infection [42].

Regardless of the cause, all lower extremity ulcers are associated with retrograde or reduced blood flow, vessel wall thickening, reduced perfusion of the skin and soft tissues, edema, ischemia and subsequent necrosis. In both CVD and DM, the mechanism of ulcer formation involves a sequence of pathophysiologic steps that are thought to include a reduction in vessel flow due to obstruction and/or reflux, persistent vessel hypertension, and subsequent increased capillary filtration and interstitial fluid load. Added to this is possible lymphatic dysfunction, wherein fluid load overwhelms the lymphatic capacity allowing accumulation of interstitial fluid, macromolecules, and cytokines leading to edema, breakdown of subcutaneous tissue and ulcer formation [32, 33, 46].

Obesity is a risk factor for the development of both DM and CVD [1]. Overweight patients may develop clinical signs of CVD, even without pathological changes on duplex ultrasound. This may be due to hemodynamic disturbances from increased intra-abdominal pressure and muscle pump deficiency, but may also result from the proinflammatory effects of obesity. Adipose tissue distribution plays a key role in the development of adverse effects in obese patients, and a key factor appears to be the inflammatory cell population in adipose tissue. Healthy adipose tissue secretes a number of vasoactive adipokines and anti-inflammatory cytokines, and changes to this secretory profile will contribute to pathogenesis in obesity. Perivascular adipocytes differ substantially from other fat cells with regard to mRNA expression and protein production of angiogenic factors. It seems therefore that perivascular fat cells *in vitro* and *in vivo* have a much higher capacity to secrete angiogenic factors than other fat cell types. This may contribute to fat tissue growth and atherosclerotic plaque complications [16, 20, 43].

Fig. 1. Commonalities between chronic venous disease and diabetes mellitus/diabetic microangiopathies [16]

There also seems to be a common pathway related to thrombogenic factors. Recent epidemiological studies have explored the association between DM, VTE, arterial thromboembolism (coronary heart disease including myocardial infarction and stroke) and atherosclerosis (Fig. 2).

For arterial disease, some of these risk factors may be «atherogenic» (promoting progression of occlusive atherosclerosis), while others may be «thrombogenic» (promoting rupture of atheromatous plaques and superadded thrombosis) [18]. «Thrombotic» risk factors may increase the risk of VTE as well as arterial thromboembolism, whereas «atherogenic» risk factors may be more relevant to atherothrombosis. However, there is increasing evidence that many «arterial» risk factors are associated not only with atherosclerosis, but also with circulating markers of activated inflammation and haemostasis. Furthermore, there is increasing evidence that activation of inflammation and haemostasis plays a role in progression of atherosclerosis as well as in plaque rupture and superadded arterial thrombosis [18].

DM, on its turn, disturbs the physiological balance between coagulation and fibrinolysis, leading to a prothrombotic state hallmarked with platelet hypersensitivity, coagulation factor disorders and hypofibrinolysis [21]. Hyperglycemia and insulin resistance enhance number and aggregation of platelets through increasing von Willebrand factor (vWF) level and inhibiting anti-aggregatory efficiency of nitric oxide and prostaglandin I₂. They also upregulate levels of procoagulation mediators like tissue factor, coagulation factors FVII, FXII, FXI and FIX, fibrinogen, prothrombin, thrombin, plasminogen activator inhibitor-1 (PAI-1), and thrombin-activator inhibitor-1 [22]. Many theories on how hyperglycemia leads to hypercoagulability have already been proposed and studied [10]. First, on a cellular level, hyperglycemia and also hyperinsulinemia

increases the expression of PAI-1 on vascular smooth muscle cells in vitro, thereby increasing its concentration and activity. As a result, the activity of tissue plasminogen activator (t-PA) is reduced, thereby decreasing the fibrinolytic potential [31]. A chronic hyperglycemic state leads to high circulating levels of thrombin-antithrombin complexes (TAT), increased tissue factor procoagulant activity (TF PCA), and factor VII [45]. TF converts FVII to the activated form of VIIA. With rising levels of blood glucose and insulin, TF-PCA also proportionally increases [7]. Next, hyperglycemia directly influences the vulnerability of the vascular endothelium by affecting the glycocalyx, a protective layer of proteoglycans covering the vessel wall. This results in enhanced platelet-endothelial cell adhesion and release of coagulation factors harboured within the endothelial glycocalyx [40]. What is more, hyperglycemia is known to cause increased glycation of proteins and this may also occur in proteins involved in coagulation and fibrinolysis. Fibrin clots from patients with T2DM are denser as compared with controls and displayed an altered structure, resulting in longer clot lysis time [13]. A likely explanation for this is the possible non-enzymatic glycation of fibrin [9]. It is conceivable that other coagulation proteins are also glycated, altering their activity.

It is not entirely clear how hyperinsulinemia adds to the prothrombotic effects of hyperglycemia. However, several studies have shown an independent effect of both hyperinsulinemia and hyperglycemia on thrombotic markers and an additive effect when simultaneously present, as in DM2 or acute hyperglycemia [31, 38].

It was suggested, that hyperglycemia and hyperinsulinemia in DM affect the intrinsic coagulation pathway, with studies revealing increased factor VIII, IX, and XI levels per mmol/L rise in fasting plasma glucose [14, 39]. The Netherlands' Epidemiology of Obesity

study demonstrated that these associations remained significant after adjusting for confounding factors such as age, gender, and BMI, among others. Patients with impaired insulin sensitivity exhibited heightened synthesis of factor XII, XI, and IX in hepatocytes, coupled with a shorter activated partial thromboplastin time, possibly mediated by insulin resistance-induced low-grade inflammation [20].

What is more, the insulin resistance has been described to extend to blood platelet activity as well. Whereas insulin has an inhibiting effect on platelet activation and aggregation in healthy individuals, there are several studies that show platelets of T2DM patients to be resistant to this inhibitory effect of insulin, making them more susceptible to activation [2, 37, 44].

Thus, multiple complex pathways are likely to be involved in the induction of hypercoagulability by hyperglycemia, and its effect is more profound in combination with hyperinsulinemia. Nevertheless, in T1DM patients the specific contribution of hyperglycemia to the prothrombotic state is clearer as they lack the other risk factors that confound the relationship in T2DM patients. In a long-term follow-up study, a highly significant correlation was found between mean HbA1c in DM1 patients over the course of 18 years and impaired fibrinolysis as represented by elevated PAI-1 and decreased t-PA [21].

The pathophysiology of CVD is directly associated with hypercoagulability/thrombosis. CVD primarily occurs due to impairment of the venous walls, but it can also manifest as a reaction to thrombosis resulting in obstruction or venous reflux [18].

Capillary hypertension, as a starting point for the development of CVD, leads to increased vessel permeability and impairment of the lymphatic microcirculation. This can in turn lead to extravasation of fluid, proteins and blood cells, which then penetrate into the interstitium. Permeable fibrinogen and other proteins

form pericapillary fibrin cuffs, which act as a barrier to the diffusion of oxygen into tissue, this can induce hypoxia. Moreover, these conditions curtail healing in patients with diabetic foot syndrome and CVD. Capillary hypertension also leads to elongation and dilation of the capillaries, with blood flow retarded as a direct result. This state facilitates the adhesion and activation of leukocytes on the endothelium (especially valves), releasing enzymes and free radicals. The combined effect of these states is to initiate inflammation and damage to the venous walls and valves. Valve insufficiency contributes to dilation and elongation of the veins and the formation of varices, stagnation of the blood flow, trophic changes progression. The impaired supply of oxygen and nutrition, contributed by PAD and DM, serve to enhance CVD progression and accelerate the onset of venous ulcers [18].

Conclusions. In conclusion, although CVD and diabetic microangiopathy have different etiologies, they share risk factors as well as pathophysiologic pathways. The intersections between diabetes mellitus and CVD are not to be underestimated. Patients with CVD should always be inspected for the presence of DM, considering its presence can have a bearing on CVD symptoms, diagnostic procedures. Considering that, overlap in treatment approaches should be expected. Treatment strategies for patients presenting with CVD and/or diabetic microangiopathy should take the possible co-existence of both diseases into account, which may ultimately lead to better patient outcomes. Hopefully, the development of new treatment modalities, as well as repurposing therapeutic approaches targeting endothelial dysfunction, modification of coagulation factors, and inflammation, together with promoting lifestyle changes and adequate glycemic control, will improve outcomes for patients with CVD and DM in the near future.

Fig. 2. A simplified impression of the relationship between hyperglycemia, hyperinsulinemia and coagulation, leading to clinical outcome [22]

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